

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D2.9 Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers

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Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project investigates the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic across the 27 EU member states (MS) and the UK, with a particular focus on vulnerable and marginalised groups. One of the project outcomes is an interactive risk assessment dashboard that highlights different vulnerabilities (physical, social, economic, and informational) and their COVID-19-related consequences. The consortium undertook extensive work to appropriately define a risk framework and identify suitable data reflecting different dimensions of risk. Following data collection, processing and curation activities, the data were modelled to create the COVINFORM Risk Score, a composite indicator assigning a level of risk to each EU MS and the UK. The COVINFORM dashboard provides access to the collected data, to the COVINFORM Risk Score as well as to the insights derived from the qualitative work undertaken during the project. The dashboard provides users with different statistical graphs and colour-coded maps showing each country's levels of risk at three key time points (pre-pandemic, first-wave, second-wave) and allows them to assess the degree with which single dimensions of risk contribute to the total score. These insights will offer stakeholders the opportunity to explore their assumptions of risk, particularly for vulnerable groups, during a public health crisis and ultimately inform their future responses.

This report provides a brief description of the final COVINFORM dashboard functionalities, details on its technical implementation and an update on the dashboard requirements deriving from the end-users engagement activities. The main output of this deliverable is a video demonstrator including a walk through of the dashboard components and functionalities. This deliverable provides an update of Deliverable 2.4 'Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers' submitted at month 22.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
AWS	Amazon Web Service
CTA	Concurrent Think Aloud
CWW	Cognitive Walk-through for the Web
IP	Intellectual property
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

1 Introduction

The dashboard is the output of the activities carried out in Task 2.3 ‘Development of risk assessment tools to map the response, impact and consideration of vulnerability in each case study location’ (M7-M28), Task 2.4 ‘Exploratory scenario applications and geo-spatial map overlay with multiple layers’ (M10-M36). The deliverable provides an update on the dashboard development activities reported in Deliverable 2.4 ‘Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers’ submitted at month 22 (which included a video demonstrator of the first version of the dashboard). Several improvements have been made to the dashboard since the last deliverable. These included adding several new functionalities, improving the functionalities on existing pages, updating the visualisation of the data and of the risk scores (in parallel with the progresses made towards the creation of the COVINFORM Risk Score), designing a new page including insights from WP3’s case studies, redesigning the user interface for a more engaging and modern look and conducting extensive testing. The dashboard described in this report is the final dashboard that will be made accessible via the COVINFORM website. A video demonstrator of the dashboard is also provided at this location.

Section 2 provides an overview of the dashboard pages’ functionalities. In Section 3 we provide a summary of the end-user requirements and feedback gathered since D2.3 and an indication of how they have been addressed by the technical developers. Section 4 reports the technical implementation details, including the software and tools used, the measure implemented to ensure algorithmic robustness and accountability, testing procedures and accessibility standards implementation. Section 5 includes notes on ethical, legal and privacy considerations made in relation to the dashboard development.

2 Dashboard overview

A demonstrator video showing a walk-through the dashboard is provided together with this report and is available on [Zenodo](#).

The dashboard can be publicly accessed at this link <https://covinform.striad.trilateral.ai/>, available on the main page of COVINFORM website.

The COVINFORM dashboard is an interactive web-based application designed with multiple pages, each providing different insights into the data collected and analysed by the team during the project. An overview of the dashboard technical characteristics and a description of its pages has been provided in “D2.7 Technical Report & Database – Update”. We show below a screenshot of the latest version of the pages, highlighting the changes made since the last report. Besides the design and functional changes visible on the dashboard, a major effort has been dedicated to update all the data that the dashboard ingests and visualises, in accordance with the latest data collection and processing activities carried out alongside the dashboard front-end development.

2.1 Homepage

This is the default page when the dashboard is launched, providing information about the project and a short description on the functionality provided by each page. This page was completely redesigned since August 2023 (when D2.7 was due) following the partners’ feedback to make the text accessible to every type of user of the dashboard and to provide only key textual description, in order to make the dashboard more visually engaging and avoid overloading the user with information. Specific icons were created by SYNNO’s design team to indicate each page. The icons

become highlighted when a user hovers over them and, when clicked, they direct the user to the relevant page.

Figure 1 Dashboard homepage

2.2 Risk Assessment

This page allows users to explore the COVINFORM Risk Score. Users can select to visualise the total score ('Overall Score') or the scores of each constituting domain of risk as well as the year for which the score refers to. The selection generates a choropleth map indicating the countries level of risk, according to a 5-degree scale. Clicking on a country, a side panel with further details on the score and a pie-chart with the relative contribution of different dimensions of risk to the score is displayed. Design and functional improvements were also made to this page following partners feedback and progresses in the risk scores development:

- The colour scale of the map was adjusted to better align with the idea of risk, making it more visually indicative of varying risk levels
- The side panel was further enhanced with textual information and improved graphics
- We removed the options to select the type of weighting and aggregation to apply in the creation the score since it emerged from the different end-user evaluation that a high level of statistical knowledge would be required to meaningfully use these options. The added value this feature would bring would not outweigh the cognitive burden it would cause to the end-user. Therefore, we opted to provide only geometrically aggregated scores where domains and subdomains of risk were equally weighted. This was selected by TRI technical team, following the OECD's recommendation (*Handbook on constructing composite indicators: methodology and user guide*, JRC, 2008, OECD publishing), as the most statistically sound version of the score and the one that makes the least assumptions on the importance of the domains and subdomains of risk.

Figure 2 2 'Risk Assessment' page - user selection options

Figure 3 'Risk Assessment' page – colour-coded geographic map and side panel with details on country's score and risk breakdown

2.3 Geospatial Plots

The geospatial plots tab allows users to select the single indicators included in the risk framework and to visualise them for the different years and disaggregation available (for some indicators, values broken down by age, gender or other characteristics are provided). Main improvements made to this page were the inclusion of additional information on the source of the data (and links to the specific dataset) and short text explaining the reasons for data gaps.

Figure 4 'Geospatial Plots' page with colour-coded map of the indicator and side panel with details on data source and bar chart with historic values of the selected indicator

2.4 Indicators Comparison

On this page, the user can visualise, on a scatter plot, how two indicators compare against each other over the years, for a selected country.

Figure 5 'Indicator Comparison' page - user selection options

2.5 COVID-19 Trends

This page generates two plots with daily and weekly time series of COVID-19 specific data, mostly epidemiological indicators. Disaggregation options are also available, and users can select to visualise data for one country or compare trends of two countries against each other.

Figure 6 'COVID-19 Trends' page - two examples of time series data

2.6 Case Study

This page provides insights on the case studies carried out by COVINFORM partners. This page has been heavily redesigned following users' feedback. It has been made clearer, via a map and textual information, the specific location and geographic granularity of the case study. The image with the theoretical framework used to analyse the case study has been removed from the dashboard since it was judged too complex to be quickly understood by non-specialist users. A link to the methodology, including the framework image, has been added instead. SYNYO's design team has created images for each case study, each visually representing specific characteristics of the population group the case study analysed. The speech bubbles including the key quotes extracted from the interviews have been made more intuitive to explore.

Figure 7 'Case Study' page - top part of the page with case study selection options and case study design information

Figure 8 'Case Study' page – bottom part of the page with interactive interview quotes (speech bubbles), lesson learnt and policy recommendation

2.7 Knowledge Repository

The knowledge repository page provides a visual interface to the COVINFORM Knowledge Repository. It allows users to search through and filter a wide range of resources gathered and generated during the project. The search can be done by keywords and different filter criteria can be applied (e.g., search by author name or by type of document). In the last months of development, additional resources were added, and the filters order and search logic have been made more intuitive following users' suggestions.

Browse a collection of COVID-19 related resources created or recommended by the COVINFORM project

Enter texts to search by Keywords

Search the COVINFORM Knowledge Repository

Select to search either by Keywords, Document Name or Authors.

Keywords

Select which document type of unstructured data to search

All Document Types

All Years

All Topics

Bi-monthly report 01 – COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts
By Elena Ambrosetti, Marina Zannella, Diotima Bertel, Su Anson, Alberto Hernández Tejedor
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/01/COVINFORM-Bi-Monthly-Report-01-A4-1.0.pdf>

Bi-monthly report 02 – COVID-19 vaccination campaign in COVINFORM countries: infographics & best practices
By Elena Ambrosetti, Marina Zannella, Itamar Laist, Chaim Rafalowski
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/03/COVINFORM-Brochure-A4-Bi-Monthly-Report-2.pdf>

Bi-monthly report 03 – A Glimpse of the Lessons Learned During the COVID-19 Pandemic
By Dailia Antunes, José Manuel Palma-Oliveira
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/06/COVINFORM-Brochure-A4-Bi-Monthly-Report-3.pdf>

Bi-monthly report 07 – Viruses of the mind. Coping and joking about COVID-19
By Diotima Bertel, Viktoria Adler
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2022/02/COVINFORM-Brochure-A4-Bi-Monthly-Report-7-Viruses-of-the-mind.-Coping-and-joking-about-COVID-19-1.0.pdf>

Bi-Monthly Report 04 – COVID-19: Findings on the Governmental Responses in COVINFORM countries

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Figure 9 'Knowledge Repository' page – users selection options and filters

2.8 Info-boxes

The top right side of each page includes an ‘info icon’ that, when clicked, shows an information box explaining what the user sees on the page and how they can explore it. The info-box pops up every time the user visit a page for the first time, to allow them to have the necessary information needed to use the page functionalities before attempting to use it. Since the last technical report, the information provided in these boxes and their design have been further enhanced by the TRI team, with the support of SINUS to ensure appropriate wording and understandability of content. Focus has been put on providing information on aspects, notions and terminology that were deemed particularly unclear by the end-users during the different evaluation activities. This was particularly relevant for the risk page where, owing to the intrinsic complexity of the risk assessment methods underlying the visual insights, additional explanations were needed.

Risk Assessment

On this page you can find the ‘risk scores’ broken down by the constituent domain and subdomain scores of each country and their ranks in comparison to other countries.

What is the ‘risk score’?

The COVINFORM Risk Score is a composite indicator obtained by a mathematical combination of four different dimensions or domains of risk - Threat, vulnerability, consequences and resilience.

These domains all have an associated score, which can be further broken down into subdomains scores, each encompassing different indicators. For instance, the ‘economic’ subdomain of the ‘vulnerabilities’ domain of risk is composed of: GDP, population living in poverty, income inequality, population with precarious employment. The hierarchic representation of the risk score is shown in the picture.

The Overall Risk Score is expressed by the following formula:

$$Risk\ Score = Threat^{0.25} \times Vulnerability^{0.25} \times Consequences^{0.25} \times Resilience^{0.25}$$

Find here additional information: [risk framework table – indicators details – methodology](#).

How to use this tool?

To use this tool, please select the reference year for which data is displayed. The options are 2019, 2020 and 2021. You can either look at the Overall Score, or look at the individual domains, namely Threat, Vulnerability, Consequences, and Resilience. Clicking each of these buttons will bring up a map, where EU member states and the UK is clickable. When you select a country, a box of information will pop up including the risk (or domain) quintile and rank (indicating the country’s level of risk) and a pie chart showing the relative contribution of different components of risk to the scores.

[Close](#)

Figure 10 Info-box for the ‘Risk Assessment’ tab, including key information on the risk scoring methodology, link to additional resources and a quick guide on how to interact with the page

3 Mapping end-users feedback to requirements

The COVINFORM dashboard was co-designed in collaboration with project partners and end-users. Under task 2.5, led by SINUS, we carried out several activities to gather end-users’ requirements and evaluate the dashboard usability and functionalities. The requirements and feedback generated by these activities directly informed the development of the dashboard and ensured alignment between the technical development and feasibility and the end-users’ expectations. The details of these activities are reported in ‘D2.5 User Guide (M36)’ which includes detailed description of the user evaluation methodologies adopted, namely an adaptation of the cognitive walkthrough for the web (CWW) and the concurrent think-aloud (CTA). The main end-users’ engagement and evaluation activities carried out were:

- **Workshop 1: requirements specifications (online, July 2021, M8).** The aim was to gather general needs of the different stakeholders to support the identification of the relevant datasets, indicators and models that would inform the COVINFORM Risk Score and Dashboard.
- **Workshop 2: First CWW (Athens, October 2022, M11).** During this session, partners had the chance to play with the first version of the dashboard which allowed them to identify major issues and bugs, highlight functionalities of interests and gaps as well as more broadly discussing the desired improvements and focus areas.
- **Workshop 3: CWW – case study tab (online, July 2023, M24).** This session was used primarily to collect feedback on the case study tab. During the consortium meeting in Berlin (May 2023) TRI presented ideas and mock-ups on how qualitative data (e.g., case study findings and interviews quotes) could be included in the dashboard and gathered requirements via a questionnaire. During the CWW session, we presented partners with the first version of the case study page, which was designed based on the gathered partners feedback.
- **Workshop 4: validation workshop – risk assessment (Antwerp, October 2023, M36).** The final validation exercise was carried out during the consortium meeting in Antwerp. The sessions focussed on evaluating the risk assessment page as this was the dashboard's component where major improvements were made since the previous workshop and where the technical team effort would be allocated in the last weeks of development. This session served also to identify minor design and user experience issues and small features changes that the technical team could address within the project timeline.
- **Individual usability testing: CTA (online, October 2023, M36).** Usability interviews were carried out with 12 external stakeholders. The feedback from these sessions helped to identify further design and user experience issues and were particularly useful to assess the understanding of the text and plots displayed for users not familiar with the COVINFORM project.

After each workshop, TRI team gathered and reviewed the feedback and 'translated' them into technical requirements each referring to a desired dashboard feature (broadly intended as addition of a new feature or an improvement of an existing one). The requirements were recorded on a table, regularly updated based on partners' feedback and issues identified by TRI developers' team. The team assigned a priority label to each requirement and an estimation of the time and effort that implementing the desired feature would require. While we valued and acknowledged all the feedback, some of them were deemed technically unfeasible to implement within the project timeline or fell outside of the scopes of the project. Requirements considered out-of-scope for the project or technical unfeasible were also marked and recorded for future consideration in potential COVINFORM's follow-up projects. We report in the table below the main feedback and technical requirements generated during the end-user evaluation activities and how we addressed them in development. Additional details on the workshops feedback and recommendation can be found in 'D2.5 - User Guide'.

The outcomes of the first workshop have been reported in D2.4. During the workshop and further discussions with the consortium it was determined that the primary users of the dashboard would be researchers and policymakers as well as practitioners in public-health-related fields such as risk communication (health practitioners have been excluded from the target end-user group because the dashboard does not offer the type of granular, real-time, situationally-specific data that would assist them in crisis response planning on a day-to-day level).

It was assessed during the workshop in Athens that the risk assessment and the case study pages are the key added value of the COVINFORM dashboard. Therefore, TRI technical team prioritised the implementation of features related to these two pages, to ensure the improvement of the most

exploitable component of the dashboard. The end-user workshop highlighted the need to provide clear and transparent explanations on how the risk score is obtained, what is the meaning of the score values and the meaning of the domains and subdomains of risk presented. The risk assessment page was designed to provide the insights on risk, derived by the consortium through extensive research on risk theory and statistical knowledge on the composite index. Displaying these insights in an accessible yet accurate way was a challenging task due to the complexity embedded in the risk definitions. The end-user feedback was essential to iteratively refine the way in which this knowledge could be made more easily digestible hence leading to higher end-user engagement with the page.

Table 11 Map of the end-user requirements and feedback from workshop to COVINFORM dashboard technical requirements

Topic	Requirement / feedback	Workshop	Action
General	The key added value of the dashboard lies in the risk assessment and case study tab	Athens	Functional and design improvements of the 'risk assessment' and 'case study' tabs were prioritised.
General	Users need an explanation to understand how to navigate the dashboard and interpret its outputs	Athens	A homepage with an overview of each page was added. An info icon was added to each page. When clicked, a pop-up with explanation appears. Additionally, a short text with information on how to use the input boxes, filters and drop down was added.
Risk assessment	Users want to link the risk framework to specific case studies. On the risk page, there could be pins to country's case studies linking to the case study report	Athens	Initial efforts to include links to the case study reports were made. However, in follow-up discussions with partners, it was agreed that showing local level, group-specific insights (from the case study) together with national aggregated statistics would be misleading. It was therefore agreed to provide the case study insights on a separate tab.
Downloads	Users want to be able to download plots with titles for inclusion in reports and other documents	Athens, Antwerp	Option to download plots have been added in the indicator comparison tab and COVID-19 Trends. Implemented the functionality to download geospatial plots presented technical challenges that could not be overcome within the project timeline.
Downloads	Users want to download the data in Excel format	Athens, Brussels	We added links to the specific datasets from which indicators of interest were extracted. A spreadsheet with the risk, domain, subdomain scores and the indicator values used in the computation is also linked for users' to download.
General	Users want to integrate on the dashboard text from the deliverables	Athens	Links to the public deliverables have been added in the Knowledge repository page. The info box in the risk page also links to the risk assessment methodology described in past deliverables. The case study page includes text on study design and learnings drawn from 'WP3 - Case Study Design and Evaluation' reporting.

General	Users want to have the dashboard available on mobile devices	Athens	Not feasible within project timeline
Data	Users want to know the data source to trust the outputs	Athens, Antwerp, CTA	Link to the dataset from which the displayed indicator is derived is provided in the hovering info in the geospatial plots. A link with details on data sources and processing is provided in the risk page info box.
General	The meaning of some words is unclear, or words are too technical	Athens	All the text showed was reviewed by different TRI members and by SINUS, at different stages of development. A final review of all the text was performed before final submission.
Risk assessment	Users want to visualise specific domains of risks	Athens	We allow users to visualise the total risk score or the score of each domain of risk. Additionally, in the hover for each country, we show the contribution of each domain and sub-domain of risk to the total.
Indicator comparison	Users want to compare more than two countries	Athens	This functionality has been deprioritised as it does not belong to the priority pages
Risk assessment	It was difficult for users to assess which weighting system to use for creating the risk score and the type of mean used in aggregation (arithmetic vs geometric). Understanding the meaning of these options was also challenging.	Athens, Antwerp, CTA	It was decided to not provide users with the options to modify the risk score by choosing different weighting systems and averaging methods. A unique version of the risk score is provided which was chosen based on theoretic and statistical considerations.
Risk assessment	Users want to understand better how the score is obtained, the data sources and what the domains of risk mean	Athens, Antwerp, CTA	Textual explanation for the overall score and domain of risk were added. The info box on the page provides the risk score formula, a risk framework graph and links to the detailed data collection, processing and modelling methodologies.
General	Users want to visualise data broken down by different population groups	Athens	Not feasible due to unavailability of demographic granular data.
Data	Users want the data displayed to be updated dynamically and include more recent data (after 2021)	Antwerp, CTA	Not feasible within the project timeline and budget.
Homepage	Information presented is complex and requires too much prior knowledge	WS3	Homepage was completely redesigned between August and September 2023 to improve clarity.
Case study	The displayed social, economic, political setting framework is too dense and complex, requiring specialised academic knowledge	WS3	The case study page was redesigned during September and October 2023 to improve clarity and usability. Focus was given on the lessons learnt and interview quotes as we found these elements generated higher engagement.
Case study	Users want more details on the case study location and methodology.	WS3	More information was added to the page info box. A link to the research methods and the case study reports was added. A map showing the case study location was added.

Risk assessment	Users didn't understand the meaning of colours	CTA	Colour scheme was changed from blue-green-yellow to yellow-orange-red scale to more clearly indicate different levels of risk
General	Users couldn't find the info boxes or other clickable elements	CTA	Info box logo was redesigned and design changes were made to make clickable elements more visible
Risk assessment and geospatial plots	Names of the countries on the map are in country's language	CTA	This functionality is technically challenging due to the unavailability of map layers with English names of the format required by dashboard. Custom solution would be required to fix this but it was considered not feasible within the project timeline.
General	Size and appearance – lower banner doesn't make visible other parts of the site and scrolling in not intuitive	CTA	Several navigation improvements were made in the last weeks of development and the lower banner issues were fixed
General	Disaggregation options showing 'N/A' are confusing	CTA	Only available disaggregation is shown for each selected indicator (making hence unnecessary showing box with 'N/A' – not available)
Indicator comparisons	Users don't find intuitive to hover over the graph to see country names and data sources are missing	CTA	Replacing dots by country names in the scatter plot was tested but resulted in an unclear visualisation due to overlapping names. In the hover, the data source of the indicator was added.
Knowledge repository	Some links refer to documents on COVINFORM Google Drive, not accessible by external users	CTA	Links to public documents on Google Drive were replaced with links to the same documents uploaded on Zotero

4 Technical specifications

4.1 Implementation

4.1.1 Backend

Data visualised on the dashboard is hosted using TRI's STRIAD¹ platform in an Amazon Web Services (AWS) S3 object storage bucket². This storage service offers industry-leading scalability, data availability, security, and performance. Alongside the hosting of the dashboard itself on an AWS EC2³ instance (see [Deployment and Security](#)) this ensures rapid data transfer between system components – data transfer speed is a bottleneck for the loading speed of the dashboard, and so this is an important usability optimisation. The architecture of this data storage system is detailed in Section 4 of the D2.7 Technical Report.

¹ <https://trilateralresearch.com/striad-platform>

² <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>

³ EC2 is a cloud computing platform offered by AWS <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/>

Data is imported using the S3 API and converted to a Pandas DataFrame (a data structure implemented in Python), with visualisation primarily conducted using the Python's Plotly⁴ and Dash⁵ libraries. Processing steps performed on the dashboard perform the transformation and filtering of datasets according to user-selected requirements, with the majority of pre-processing steps including collation, cleaning, reshaping, and averaging conducted before data is uploaded to the S3 service (further details available in Section 5 of the D2.7 technical report). This improves the speed and usability of the dashboard by reducing the processing that must be conducted in real-time. After loading the requested data onto the server instance running the dashboard (isolated from other running processes via the containerisation process outlined in [Deployment and Security](#)) the data is filtered according to user-defined settings and transformed into the format required for the visualisations on the current tab, and the visualisation then produced in real-time and displayed for the user.

An index of the knowledge repository is also stored in the dashboard S3 bucket for rapid access. This index is then searched using user-defined parameters when interacting with the “Knowledge Repository” page using a custom library developed by TRI, optimised for search operations on the type of data storage system in use. Search results are returned using data stored in the index with external links providing direct access to reports, articles, and other items held within the knowledge repository.

4.1.2 Frontend

The frontend of the dashboard allows users to interact with the different pages that entail unique features and functionalities. The user can have tailored views of visualisations and plots that are presented using the pre-processed data (see [Backend](#)) using the filter and options provided. The dashboard was developed utilising Dash, a Python web framework that leverages both Python and JavaScript⁶ programming to visually represent the key findings and insights. This dashboard front-end is designed as a multi-page application to accommodate multiple features which can be accessed via the available links within the dashboard or by directly visiting its unique URL.

4.2 Code management and robustness

TRI technical team followed best software practices for the development and management of the dashboard codebase (the complete set of source code that is used to run a software application).

4.2.1 Version Control

The COVINFORM dashboard's source code was developed on a Git⁷ repository hosted on TRI's servers for version control. The team used a well-defined version control strategy. New dashboard features, were implemented first on isolated branches of the code repository, ensuring that no code changes would affect the work of other feature developers or impact the usability of the main codebase before testing had been completed. Regular commits (or 'uploads' of the updated code on the codebase) were encouraged to ensure code changes and the reasons for those changes could be easily tracked and the point at which any bugs were introduced more readily identified.

⁴ Plotly Technologies Inc. Collaborative data science. Montréal, QC, 2015. <https://plot.ly>.

⁵ <https://dash.plotly.com/>

⁶ <https://www.javascript.com/>

⁷ Git is a code version control tool, TRI used a version of it implemented on Bitbucket, an industry-leading Git system on cloud <https://bitbucket.org/product>

4.2.2 Code Standards

To ensure the code was of high quality, readable, and consistent, we followed a documented coding standard and style guide for all dashboard development. Python code (the vast majority of the codebase) was formatted using Black⁸, a code formatter that ensures consistency across the codebase and between developers by disallowing variations in formatting. Naming conventions adhered to the PEP8 style guide. Code comments and documentation were well-defined and the use of comments encouraged, particularly where other team members may not be familiar with a particular library's inbuilt functionality or logic flow.

4.2.3 Testing, Code Review, and Bug Fixes

Testing of new features was first conducted by the developer of a particular feature through local deployment of the dashboard and rigorous testing against multiple datasets – this was largely conducted manually due to the resourcing requirements of the development process and the difficulty of automating the testing of interactive components. Any bugs identified through this testing was documented for later patching. Once the development of a new feature was complete and the code had been tested, a formal request for code review was sent to other developers. While this number changes throughout the course of the project, at a minimum two developers had to review, test independently, and approve the changes before the branch (where the feature was developed) could be merged into the main codebase. This review would address not only whether the intended functionality had been achieved, but also aimed to identify bugs or future logical errors, uphold code standards and quality, and ensure consistency across the codebase.

Bug fixes were implemented in much the same way as new features, with a similar development and review process. Comprehensive bug identification and fixing was a large component of the final months of the dashboard development process. All the TRI team members working on WP2 were regular users of the dashboard. Testing done by SINUS team (as part of preparation for the user evaluation workshops) were beneficial for bug-fixing. Usability tests (as described in D2.5 User Guide) were an additional excellent resource in identifying bugs, assessing desire for new features, and most importantly for assessing desired optimisations and improvements in accessibility – frustrations with design elements, loading speeds, and user experience allowed us to identify which elements of the dashboard on which to focus optimisation efforts.

4.2.4 Deployment and Security

The public version of the dashboard is hosted using TRI's STRIAD platform on an Amazon Web Services (AWS) EC2 server instance which implements the highest security standards. Using AWS cloud services ensures that security patches (fixes of security vulnerabilities) are implemented automatically, and server maintenance requires no downtime (period of time during which the server is not accessible). Access to this server, as well as access to the S3 bucket hosting the dashboard data, is tightly restricted and managed using the AWS tools for secure access management.

To ensure consistency in configuration when new versions of the dashboard are deployed the dashboard is deployed using Docker⁹, a virtualisation service that uses containers (i.e., standalone 'packages' of code containing the software and any setting needed to run the software) for quickly and

⁸ <https://pypi.org/project/black/>

⁹ <https://www.docker.com/>

easy deployment of new dashboard versions. Further, an automated pipeline to ensure that the public version of the dashboard always contains the latest tested and approved feature updates and bug fixes. This containerisation process also improves the security of the dashboard by isolating the processes involved in running the dashboard from the rest of the instance.

4.2.5 Environment Management

Both `conda`¹⁰ and `pip`¹¹ were used to manage the installation of the Python libraries necessary to run the dashboard. By isolating the installed libraries and environmental setup from the rest of the development machine being used, bugs become easier to identify as they will be dependent only on the condition of the development environment. Sharing configuration files for `conda` and `pip` environments also meant that changes in the libraries required to run the dashboard code (such as when introducing a new feature that required a new library) can be easily shared between the development team.

4.3 Accessibility and UX

We ensure that the entire application strictly adheres to the *Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1 AA* accessibility standards throughout the feature implementation process. Based on these guidelines, we created an accessibility requirement checklist that guided our development of accessibility features for the COVINOFRM dashboard. In the context of the dashboard, accessibility refers to our responsibility to create an inclusive user experience, where users can access, understand, and interact with the content and features we offer. The guidelines refer to four main principles that web content must adhere to be considered accessible (content must be *perceivable*, *operable*, *understandable* and robust). We achieve these in the following ways:

1. **Perceivable:** we ensure that all information and user interface components are presented using multiple modalities to enhance accessibility. This includes providing alternative text for images and non-text content, such as data visualisations, to facilitate use with screen readers and keyboard navigation.
2. **Operable:** the dashboard has been designed so that content can be easily navigated and interacted via interactive elements and buttons. It has also been designed so that it can be operated using mouse, keyboard and assistive technologies.
3. **Understandable:** To make the dashboard understandable, we ensured that every user interface component and the structure of the content is easy to apprehend (this has been iteratively achieved by gathering end-users feedback). There is a consistent and clear navigation and labelling pattern throughout the application.
4. **Robust:** We've developed our dashboard using industry-standard web technologies such as `Bootstrap`¹², an open-source front-end framework to create a responsive design and interactive elements. We have also ensured that it is compatible with a wide range of browsers and assistive technologies. This guarantees that the dashboard will remain functional and accessible as technology evolves.

The accessibility standard of the dashboard has been implemented and tested using a variety of tools and browser extensions. Examples include the Wave Evaluation tool¹³, Chrome Lighthouse¹⁴, and

¹⁰ <https://docs.conda.io/en/latest/>

¹¹ <https://pypi.org/project/pip/>

¹² <https://getbootstrap.com/>

¹³ <https://wave.webaim.org/>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/GoogleChrome/lighthouse>

Firefox Accessibility Inspector¹⁵, these plug-in validators help developer to spot accessibility issues that would then be fixed in development. To ensure comprehensive accessibility, we also employed the Chrome extension Screen Reader¹⁶ to test the dashboard's capabilities with screen readers. Furthermore, we conducted thorough keyboard testing to verify that all features are fully navigable using only keyboard inputs. These assessments collectively affirm that our Dashboard meets accessibility standards. Finally, the developer team regularly engaged Trilateral Research's Senior UI/UX designer to gather recommendations and feedback on visually simplifying complex content and dense information.

5 Ethical, Privacy and Legal Considerations

The use of the Dashboard does not entail the processing of any personal data as defined in the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. All the quantitative data used and displayed are publicly available. TRI carefully reviewed the terms of use of each data source to ensure that their use and visualisation were compliant with the source requirements. Sources which required explicit approval from the organisations owning the data were contacted and their approval obtained. The data sources have been linked on the dashboard and details on their processing have been reported on supplementary technical documentation, uploaded on Zenodo and provided to end users via links, accessible via the dashboard. The interview quotes showed on the 'Case Study' tabs are anonymous and approval to collect and process them have been obtained within WP3 activities. TRI team consulted TRI's legal advisor to ensure proper IP management, citations of software licences as well as defining the rules governing the use of the dashboard. Based on this, the legal advisor drafted the 'COVINFORM Terms of Use', visibly linked at the bottom of each dashboard page.

6 Conclusions

This short report describes the technical development carried out to finalise the COVINFORM dashboard (Task 2.3 and Task 2.4) and to embed into it the feedback and requirements obtained via end-user engagement activities (Task 2.5). The dashboard here described and shown in the associated video demonstrator is the final and main output of WP2 and one of the key outputs of COVINFORM project as it was designed to incorporate insights generated by the different quantitative (e.g., the development of the COVINFORM Risk Score and associated analysis thereof) and qualitative research activities (e.g., risk assessment framework definition, case study research on selected vulnerable groups). The dashboard will be a valuable resource for researchers and other interested stakeholders, accessible on the COVINFORM website for at least one year following the project ending (extension to this period will be evaluated based on the interested and exploitation opportunities generated by the dashboard).

7 References

7.1 Literature

¹⁵ https://firefox-source-docs.mozilla.org/devtools-user/accessibility_inspector/

¹⁶ <https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/screen-reader/kgejglhnpjiefppelpmljglcjboiplfn>

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7.2 Websites

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